

Parubai v. State of Maharashtra

(Case Commentary)

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I. LITIGATION HISTORY :-

The appellant, Parubai, had approached the Supreme Court post the decisions given by the High Court and the Trial Court. The High Court had dismissed the appeal and the decision given by the Sessions Judge. Both the Sessions Court and the High Court had convicted the appellant for committing offences under Section 302 (murder) and Section 436 (mischief by fire or any explosive substance with the intention of destroying house etc.) of the Indian Penal Code (hereinafter referred to as 'IPC').

II. TYPES OF EVIDENCE BASED ON CLASSIFICATION :-

According to the case at hand, there are essentially four types of evidences which have come to light before the Hon'ble Court.

Firstly, the *Circumstantial evidence*. The Sessions Court took into consideration the circumstantial evidence of the frock of Nikita, which had been recovered from the crime scene, as well as the can, which smelt of kerosene, which was found in the bushes nearby. The Sessions court also considered the circumstantial evidence that had been tendered to them by PW-1 and PW-3 that if Parubai was also sleeping next to Mandabai, and if the house did catch fire, then Parubai should also have some burn injuries, which were not there.

The High Court in its judgement had, on the basis of the circumstances, and by taking recourse to Section 106 of the Indian Evidence Act, 1872 (hereinafter referred to as 'The Act') had held that Parubai had a responsibility of providing information about the situation, which was in her special knowledge, under which the fire had been caused. Not doing so resulted in the court gaining insights from the circumstantial evidence that the appellant had sprinkled kerosene on Mandabai and her children and then ignited the fire.

Moreover, the Supreme Court noted that the entire house and the cowshed which was built next to it had caught fire. Out of one of the three rooms, one was occupied by Piraji Mankari, who is referred to as PW-3, and his family. If the situation be so, then Piraji Mankari and his family should also have sustained some burn injuries, which was apparently not the case.

Secondly, the ***Oral evidence***. The oral dying declarations that was made to one of the sisters of Chhaya, who was one of the deceased, is one of the oral evidences. Furthermore, the statements that has been recorded by the courts of the witnesses also fall under this classification.

Thirdly, the ***Documentary evidence***. There are several documentary evidences which were recorded by the High Court. The report of the chemical analysis done on Nikita's frock was proof the residues of kerosene, which aided the court in affirming that kerosene was used in order to set the fire. The chemical analysis report can be further clubbed under ***forensic evidence***. Furthermore, the Marriage Certificate was produced before the court which was used to show the registration of the marriage of Parubai and Gulab, as done on February 18, 2006. Moreover, the agreement taken by Mandabai from Gulab that after his second marriage, he will continue to maintain Mandabai and her children and that he will transfer certain amount of land in Mandabai's name is also documentary evidence.

Last, but not the least is the ***Non-Judicial evidence***. This includes the extra-judicial confession that was apparently given by the appellant to the father-in-law that, admitting that she was the one who had set the fire by sprinkling kerosene.

III. POSITION OF COURT ON DIFFERENT EVIDENTIARY VALUE OF EVIDENCE :-

The trial court, on scrutinizing the evidence, had decided that the evidence provided by the father-in-law to accuse the appellant and the mother-in-law were insufficient, and ergo, their charges could not be proven. Thus, it had a *low evidentiary* value.

Taking into consideration the evidence provided by Parubai (PW-1) and her mother-in-law (PW-3), that the appellant had also been sleeping along with the deceased individual and that in case the house did catch fire, then the appellant should also have suffered burn injuries. As she had come out of the house unscathed, thus she was guilty. The Sessions Court had taken note of this evidence and considered it to be valid while convicting the appellant. The High Court however, discarded the evidence of Parubai and considered it to be of *low evidentiary* value.

Furthermore, the extra-judicial confession that had been made by the appellant to the father-in-law by her that she had ignited the fire by spilling kerosene was rejected by the High Court. The High Court gave the rationale that Gajanan, the father-in-law, who was also the individual

who had given the information could not have gladly given assent to the appellant as becoming the second wife of his son, when Mandabai was already his wife. Ergo, the court believed that this extra-judicial confession had very low evidentiary value in itself.

In respect to the evidence given by the Sub-Inspector Phad (PW-8) and Vijay (PW-4), i.e., regarding the finding of the kerosene can when Parubai was under police custody. The High Court considered this can to be of *low evidentiary* value, as it had not been sent for chemical inspection and analysis. The Sessions Court however, had accepted the can to be of material evidence.

Moreover, the oral dying declaration that had been made to Chhaya (PW-2), one of the sisters of the deceased, was considered to be of *low evidentiary* value by both the Sessions Court and the High Court. However, the dying declaration that had been made to the police head constable was considered as noteworthy.

The can that had apparently been smelling of kerosene was held to be of *low evidentiary* value by the High Court as the can had not undergone the process of chemical analysis, as well as the fact that the circumstances in which it had been found.

The Supreme Court held the registration of the second marriage post the agreement between Gulab and Mandabai to be of *low evidentiary* value in proving that Parubai was guilty of the crime.

IV. CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF SUPREME COURT JUDGEMENT BASED ON THE EVIDENCE:-

Wherefore, in the light of the evidence that had been presented before the Hon'ble Supreme Court and after taking into consideration all the evidences and perusing the judgements of the lower courts, the Supreme Court adjudged that Parubai was not guilty.

It is settled that this incident is extremely unfortunate and grotesque. The main issue in the present case was to ascertain whether the chain of situations and circumstances was complete in order to hold the appellant guilty. It can be clearly seen that the High Court had held the appellant to be guilty more so on probability, instead of arriving at a conclusion which is beyond reasonable doubt. Fundamentally, the rationale given by the High Court traces its roots to surmises and conjectures.

Apparently, there were equal probabilities, which raise the question as to whether Parubai could be held liable solely because she did not sustain any injuries. The Court opined that it is natural for any human that in case of such an accident or an incident, the reflex action is to save oneself and move away from such an occurrence. It seems probable that the linkages which are present in the chain of circumstances are pertinent to be showcased so as to prove the liability of the accused when it comes to circumstantial evidence¹.

Additionally, it is noteworthy that just in case the chemical report is accepted, then there was nothing present on the record to link it to the conjecture that Parubai had sprinkled kerosene or that there was kerosene on Mandabai's daughter's frock. Further, there existed equal situations and circumstances which raise the question as to whether Parubai could be held liable solely because she did not sustain any injuries. As per the Court, it is natural for any human to save themselves and run away from any such occurrence. The court further added that the linkages which are present in the chain of circumstances are pertinent to be established so as to prove the liability of the accused when it comes to circumstantial evidence. Mere suspicion will not suffice unless the circumstantial evidence given by the prosecution leads to the conclusion that it "*must be true*" and not "*may be true*".²

Additionally, the Court found that Mandabai, who survived for a day, made no accusations whatsoever, which includes the appellant as well. Her claim was unequivocal: the house was engulfed in flames, trapping her and her children within. Moreover, it was established that the servant was also living in the house, and he too was unharmed. There was a lot of disagreement with the observation of the High Court that Parubai had set the house alight because her husband had executed an agreement of maintenance out of some property, in Mandabai's favour, a day prior to the appellant getting married to him. It is noteworthy that the second marriage was registered post the agreement with Mandabai, which is considered normal in such situations. Ergo, it is not the motive for committing the crime.

Lastly, albeit the appellant did not give an explanation for the fire in view of Section 106 of The Act³, the Court adjudged that Parubai's responsibility to explain have only arise given that

¹ Sharad Birdhichand Sarda v. State of Maharashtra, (1984) 4 SCC 116.

² Devilal v. State of Rajasthan, (2019) 19 SCC 447.

³ The Indian Evidence Act, 1872, §106.

there was some corroborative evidence showing that she had already awoken and had gone out of the house before the fire ignited.